

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B419
 Date: 12 November 2008
 Take Off: 11:29:58
 Landing: 16:51:38
 Flight Time 5h 21m 40s

Campaign: VOCALS – Ron Brown Case Study

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the coast of northern Chile .

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Jackie Mullholland	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Geraint Vaughan	Leeds University	
6	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM	
7	Core Chem	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
11	CAPS / 2DS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
12	AMS / CCN	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
13	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	James Bowles	Met Office	
14	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
15	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
16	MARSS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
17	Mission Scientist 3	Grant Allen	Manchester University	
18	Mission Scientist 4	Phil Brown	Met Office	
19				

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b419
 Date: 2/11/2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: Arica, Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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112006		Start-Up	0.13 kft	023	engines
112425		start taxi	0.13 kft	022	
112611		!	0.12 kft	289	ASPs opened
112958		T/O	0.49 kft	209	
112958	113646	Profile 1	0.00 - 6.0 kft	223	
113616		!	6.0 kft	262	Nevzorov / JW zero
113709	114005	Run 1	6.0 kft	262	
114011	114627	Profile 2	6.0 - 0.50 kft	262	QNH 1015 hPa
114627	115128	Run 2	0.50 - 0.44 kft	260	QNH 1015 hPa
114830		!	0.44 kft	266	Johnson Williams zero
115133	115456	Profile 3	0.43 - 3.3 kft	259	
115457	120005	Run 3	3.2 - 3.3 kft	245	
120023	120130	Profile 4	3.5 - 4.6 kft	262	
120138	120637	Run 4	4.6 - 4.5 kft	264	
120647	121139	Profile 5	4.5 - 0.50 kft	264	
121147	122229	Run 5	0.50 - 0.58 kft	258	
121347		!	0.45 kft	262	Heimann cal
122304	122539	Profile 6	1.1 - 3.5 kft	263	
122547	123604	Run 6	3.5 kft	260	
123609	123751	Profile 7	3.5 - 5.1 kft	264	
123751	124433	Profile 8	5.1 - -.05 kft	257	
124448	125718	Run 7	0.1 kft	255	100
125230		!	0.1 kft	315	Heimann cal
125725	130052	Profile 9	0.1 - 3.5 kft	308	
130222	132201	Run 8	3.5 kft	127	
132202	132354	Profile 10	3.5 - 4.9 kft	127	
132354	132849	Run 9	4.9 - 4.8 kft	145	
132743		!	4.8 kft	150	Nevzorov/JW zero
132958		!	4.8 kft	007	Heimann cal
133027	133526	Run 10	4.8 kft	331	
133800	135655	Run 11	3.2 - 3.1 kft	308	
135733	135843	Profile 11	3.1 - 2.2 kft	348	
140051		!	2.2 kft	114	Nevzorov/JW zero
140112	142140	Run 12	2.2 kft	105	
140908		!	2.2 kft	128	Heimann cal
142140	142633	Profile 12	2.2 - -.05 kft	129	

142643	144457	Run 13	0.1 kft	308
143754		!	0.1 kft	307 Heimann cal
144521	145552	Profile 13	0.40 - 9.9 kft	305
145022		!	5.2 kft	129 JW zero
145227		!	6.9 kft	128 JW zero
145552	150038	Profile 14	9.9 - 6.0 kft	126
150039	150824	Run 14	5.9 - 6.0 kft	129
150945	151341	Profile 15	5.9 - 3.9 kft	136 skimming cloud tops
151437	152155	Run 15	3.8 kft	308
152155	152759	Profile 16	3.8 - 0.05 kft	309
152514		!	1.3 kft	061 JW zero
152759	153225	Profile 17	0.05 - 4.5 kft	062
153352		!	4.5 kft	060 Nevzorov/JW zero
154048	154144	Profile 18	4.1 - 3.4 kft	072 coordinated with G1
154144	155140	Run 16	3.4 - 3.3 kft	094
154845		!	3.4 kft	091 JW zero
155140	155508	Profile 19	3.3 - 0.99 kft	091
155516	160506	Run 17	0.95 - 0.99 kft	094
160516	160910	Profile 20	1.0 - 4.5 kft	094
160856		!	4.3 kft	086 JW zero
160910	161909	Run 18	4.5 kft	084
161051		!	4.5 kft	087 Heimann cal
161915	162523	Profile 21	4.4 - 0.05 kft	088
162302		!	1.3 kft	091 JW zero
162524	163101	Profile 22	0.05 - 5.0 kft	089
163050		!	4.9 kft	089 JW zero
163101	163726	Profile 23	5.0 - 0.50 kft	089
163313		!	3.4 kft	090 JW zero
163455		!	1.9 kft	089 JW zero
163727	164225	Profile 24	0.50 - 5.0 kft	085
164332		!	5.1 kft	078 JW zero
165138		Land	0.18 kft	109
165336		!	0.18 kft	018 ASPs closed

B419 Track 12-NOV-08

SCAR -> SCDA - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-11 Expires: Thursday, 20 November 2008.
Scale: 1:1838389 (1 inch = 25.21 naut mi). Printed on 11 Nov 2008

76996;68

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

FAAM Sortie, Flight B419
Wed 12th November 2008
VOCALS Flight B419 – Ron Brown Case study

T/O **0830 local (1130 UTC)**
Land **1350 local (1650 UTC)**

Mission Scientists: Keith Bower, Grant Allen, Phil Brown, Geraint Vaughan

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile, with ops area centred on 75° W, 19° 30' S

Waypoints:

ROMEO: 75°32'21'' W, 19°5'30'' W

R1: North end-point of run 35 NM from ROMEO along Ron Brown radar radial

R2: South end-point of run 35 NM from ROMEO along Ron Brown radar radial

GOLF: 74° 30'W, 18° 30' S

Radial to operate over point ROMEO: 125 and 305 degrees

Ron Brown Contact: Marine VHF RHB guards channel 13 and 16
Or on handheld radio on 123.45 MHz

Sortie Objectives: To overfly the Ronald H Brown (RHB) cruise ship whilst on station at point ROMEO and perform a case study of the area; and intercompare radiometric and cloud instruments with measurements made by the Dornier and RHB. An in-and-below cloud trailing intercomparison will also be made with the Dornier on the outbound transit to ROMEO and a further intercomparison with the G-1 will be made in-and-below cloud on the return transit to Arica. A ground intercomparison with the C-130 will be carried out for one hour after landing.

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Near shore light marine boundary layer winds from S.

Key Instrument Details:

SWS/ARIES – as per instructions.

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

AMS – operate from Rosemount during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; operate on CVI during in cloud runs

Information:

Latest satellite image will be inserted prior to take-off

B419 12th Nov 2008

Flight patterns:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl and begin short minute run to check instrumentation, setting radial to ROMEO [15 min; T=0h 15 m]
2. Profile descent to 500 ft amsl for a 10-minute SLR run below cloud. (*Advise Dornier of the lat/lon of the start of the SLR*) [13 min; T=0h 28 m]
3. Profile ascent to in-cloud at flight level advised by mission scientist for a 10-minute SLR run. (*Advise Dornier of the lat/lon of the start of the SLR*) [11 min, T =0h 39 min]
3. Continue to point ROMEO and make contact with Ron Brown as soon as possible. (*Relay position of RHB and radar radial to the Dornier*) [36 min, T=1h 15 min]
4. At ROMEO, turn to R1 to align with RHB radar northward radial and begin 35 NM SLR run at 100 ft amsl (*Advise Dornier of the intended end point of run and coordinate the Dornier to meet us at a point on the run.*) [10m, T=1h 25 min]
5. At R1, turn toward R2 and begin a 20-minute SLR run in-cloud (100 ft below cloud top) [22m, T=1h 47 min]
6. Run 3x20-minute SLR legs between R2 and R1 at altitudes advised by the mission scientist for as long as the Dornier remains coordinated with G-LUXE [1h 06m, T=2h53m]
7. After Dornier breaks off, run a 20-minute saw-tooth profile between 50 ft and 1000 ft above cloud top, between R2 and R1 [22m, T=3h 13m]
8. Continue SLR runs between R1 and R2 at altitudes advised by the mission scientist for as long as possible before turning toward GOLF [32m, T=3h45]
9. Turn to intercept GOLF to arrive at 1240 Local [T=4h 10m]
10. At arrival at GOLF turn to fly 3x10 minute SLR runs above, in and below cloud along the 18 deg 30'S latitude line. (*Relay longitude of start and end times of each run to the G-1*) [30m, T= 4h 15m].
11. Recovery and land at Arica [T=5h 20m]

Mission Scientist's Log [VOCALS - ROM BROWN #2]

Flight No B.419 Date R/11/06 Name K. N. BOWER Page 1 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
8:20:16	KNB, 8:20	29, 8:21.29	8:22	01-8:22:39	Starting 4-1
8:22:55	"				power change over (wind directly across R/W)
8:24:46	"				Taxi (p settings 1014)
8:29:42	"				Rolling 09/03kt, START Donnie Tearing
8:30:19	"				T/O/P1 Clear Skies above - murky/cloudy on horizon - quite a bit more SO ₂ + NO _x than below
8:34:04	"				Going over dead edge now..... setting up MSci laptop.
11:37:09	R1				AMS thresholds - settings saved - no time now - down. ^{because of DO228 VC}
11:40:01	R1/P2	5.9kft	262	18°24'/70°54'	(↓ to 500ft) 812mb 17.74°/10.17C hmk/159°
11:42:46	P2	3.4kft	263	18°30'/71°6'	C1 ~ 3500ft 833mb 9.99°/2.44C 2m/s/204°
11:43:34	P2	2.7kft	262		CB ~ 2700ft, 917mb (1014 QNH) 10.84°/11.72° (setting new QNH = 1015) ^{hmk/220°}
11:46:27	P2/R2	0.5kft	260	18°30'/71°24'	P1 [S 19° 32.41' - W 071° 25.66'] → DO 228 994mb, 17.69°/12.56C 2m/s/220°
8:51:00	≡ 11 50 34 (KNB ≡ Normal)				DO 228 Will arrive port 1 12:00 _z Comms (18 KNB time = 0700 24s.) R Brown (19° 4.9 min S, 75° 32.3 min W) Heading 157° and 5.3 kts currently.
11:51:27	R2/P3	0.4kft			from 500ft. 997mb, 17.71/12.2C 1mk/212°
11:54:55	P3/R3	3.2kft	245	18°36'/71°54'	P2 (S 18° 37.43' N. 071 59.04') ^{originals (18° 33' 71 59.04)} → DO 228 Start at 3300ft in descent, 9.01/10.44C 2m/s/150°, ^{100kt}
***	Comms	DO 228			Electrical problem - intermittent power spikes *** - power inverter has gone/playing up - lost volts
12:00:01	R3/P4	3.2kft	262	18°42'/72°18'	↑ 3300ft to 1000 above CT. 8.47/9.72° 2m/s/148° ^{power - RTB 59mb}
	P4				C1 3600 ft.

[arriving RB ~ 12:11]

next run @ 3200ft

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...419 Date 12/11/08 Name KN Bower Page 2 of 11

4600ft

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12:01:29	R4E/R4	4.5kft	263	18°42'/72°24'	p=858mb 19.45°/13.11°C 2m/s/282° Above CT min
12:06:33	R4E/PS _s	4.5kft	264	18°42'/72°42'	853mb 19.11/16.95°C 2m/s/278° (WESTERL!)
12:07:20	PS	3.8kft	265	" /72°48'	CT=3600ft 850mb 14.25/15.98 1m/s/314°
12:08:03	PS	3.0kft	262	" /72°48'	CB=3100ft 903mb 9.14/16.45 2m/s/141°
					(QNH setting 1016mb)
12:11:37	PS _E /PS	0.5kft	261	18°48'/73°6'	500ft 995mb 16.66/11.33°C 4m/s/165°
12:13:00	Comm	0.4kft	260		Clouds at RB CT=1100m (ie ~3600ft) CB=750m (ie ~2460ft)
					little drizzle not reaching surface
					Cloud deck - uniform all way out to RB.
12:22:16	RS _E /P6	0.4kft	260	18°48'/73°48'	996mb 16.07/11.05°C 7m/s/160 500ft ↑ 3500ft
12:24:56	P6	2.8kft	260	18°34'/73°54'	CB=2900ft. 93mb 9.21/9.91°C 5m/s/149°
12:25:40	P6 _E /R6 _s	3.4kft	260	18°54'/74°	3500ft 893mb 7.74/10.09°C 5m/s/151°
	R6				Core Cloud CDP 270 μm ³ 12 μm φ FSSP 420-450 12-13 μm drizzle 15/litre 200 μm ZDS CAS 500-600 15 μm drizzle - not high
12:29:45	RON BROWN	COMM			Pos ⁿ 19° 27.318'S 075° 19.812W 19° 27.363'S 075° 19.790W
					19° 49 min S 75° 32.3 min W ?
					latter coords near the original points made last night - go there first
					- currently scanning 158° @ 5kts - shear -
					15mins - scanning 125, 305° around.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 419 Date 12/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 3 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12.36:04	P6/P7	↑ 3.4kft	264	18°54'/74°42'	3500ft 893mb 7.7°/10.09° 5mb/161°
12.36.39	P7	3.9kft	250	19°/74°42'	CT=4100ft 875mb 7.95/9.3° 6mb/162°
12.37.45	P7/P8	5.0kft	257	19°/74°48'	5100ft 842mb 19.0°-24.58 0mb
12.39.49	P8	3.9kft	259	19°/74°54'	CT=4000ft 876mb 18.32/-30.36 3mb/155°
					seeing lkt down still NO ₂ dropped
					clearly - measuring clean values - side CO
					O ₃
12.---					---
					Gal confirms pos'n 19° 30'
					74 30' at 12.40
					at 5000ft. ✓
					X chub -
					CB 2500
					- first pass to N - subsequent pick
					- she are not showing wind
12.44.28	P8end	50'/0kft	254	19°/75°18'	50ft 1013mb 16.95°/12.21°C 3ms/160°
12.44.38	R7	100ft/0kft	253	19°6'/75°18'	100ft 1013mb 16.92°/12.14°C 4mb/165
12.47.47	P8down	100ft/0kft	260	19°6'/75°30'	Non Brum to CHS - Visual Contact. Pics.
					R1 S 18°46.87' W 076°00.13 } Cont
					R2 S 19°29.97' W 75°01.73 } LL.
					R3 S 19°08.46' W 75°30.99' }
12.50.15	R7				4 mins for turnaround at R1
					PCASP CVI not much above 1µm !!!
12.57.17	R7/P9	0kft	308	18°42'/75°54'	100ft 1011mb 17.03/11.83 3mb/172°
13.00.12	P9	2.7kft	183	18°36'/76°6'	CB=915mb 9.04/10.07° 7mb/132°

4 mins for turn

one level vs desc to

RB

R1
RB

R2

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 419 Date 12/11/08 Name K. N. BOWER Page 4 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13.00.52	P9 end	3.4kft	131	18°42'/76°	3500ft 894mb, 7.57/10.47°C 7m/s/129°
13.02.21	R8 sub	3.4kft	127	18°42'/76°	3500 out R1 new. 893mb 7.75/10.45° 7m/s/115°
13.05.50	R8	3.4kft			New OT. new.
					Core Abund: - CDP = 200 cm ³ ϕ 20 μm FSSP = 250 cm ³ ϕ 20 19 μm ZDC = 20/l 200 μm CAS = 450 cm ³ & 15-20 μm LWC = 0.7 - pretty high.
13:08					(about 2hrs left new...)
					M5i4 - strange wind ?
					tower... 710 0700 20s → 804 -
					droppin sandes on high level return - C130 ✓
13:12:07	R8 below	3.4kft	127	19°06' 75°30'	710 1st over head - low level all ways.
					M2-M4 - winds are light
					M2 - option - find point above cloud - perform number reciprocal legs ~ 5 min duration - along mean wind direction - check wind calibrations
					M3 - CO vs latitude - reasonable gradient 60-66 CO reasonably stable ??
					<u>NB</u> One way out - passed through plume <u>NB</u>
13.21.58	R8 end / P10 sub	3.4kft	128	19°24'/75°	3500ft 893mb 7.54/10.29° 6m/s/108°
13.22.30	P10	3.8kft	128	19°30'/76°	(T=3900ft 881mb 8.87/9.78° 4m/s/101°
13.23.40	P10 end / R9	4.7kft	137	19°30'/74°54'	4900ft 849mb 15.75/-27.67 1m/s/98°
					on profile we passed through 11c CO/O ₃ at bottom of layer - CO 70ppb

25 min =
4 runs
+ 20 min
(maybe more)

13.08 ~ 2hrs left
15.08 back to G1 R/V ... 2hrs - M3 - yip
1hrs 30 -

[90 mins - 20 cloud 70 mins
left 20 BC 50
25 BC 25 → leaves about on run
for something else]

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...⁴¹⁹..... Date 12/11/08 Name K N BOWER Page 5 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					M3- 4900ft, 849mb 19.29°/25.28° 3m/s/121°
4900ft 13.28.48	R9 end	4.5kft	150°	19°48'/74°42'	turning for reciprocal. on heading 330 now
					G1 airborne as per schedule timing OK ✓
4900ft 13.30.25	R10 start	4.5kft	332°	19°48'/74°42'	847mb 19.3°/-26.13°C 2m/s/270°
13.33				(MSc 3 from M0)	D ₀ ²²⁵ will know within hour - status op/no go
13.35.25	R10 end	4.8kft		19°30'/74°48'	4900ft → 3200ft (no problem descent - time)
					848mb 18.79°/-28.08° 2/270°
13.36.24	descent	3.7kft	252	19°30'/74°54'	C1 3900ft 882mb 8.06°/-11.38°C 3m/s/189°
3200ft 13.37.59	R11 start	3.1kft	307	19°30'/75°W	3200ft 8.15/10.81°C 903mb 2m/s/134°
[RB] 13.47.24	above RB	3.1kft	307	19°6'/75°30'	903mb 8.15/10.82°C 3m/s/170°
					Core Cloud: CDP 160-170 cm ³ ϕ 16µm
					FSSP 230 cm ³ ϕ 16µm
					drizzle 30/litre (up to 250µm) (Preliminary)
					but more stable than other runs 20-40/litre
					CAS = 400 cm ³ ϕ 14-15µm
					LWC = 0.3 g/m ³
					Core Cloud 2DS - not much drizzle.....?
					M3: Nev 0.3 g/m ³ } similar to CAS Men. JW 0.4 g/m ³ }
					LWC re quite homogeneous above 3
					- good to of LWC retrievals
				MG - R Braun	"CB from smooth forcing"
					Weak larger scale
				MG	NOAA W band
13.56.53	R11 end	3.1kft	309	18°42'/75°54'	3200ft. 903mb in cloud. 8.51/10.6° 2m/s/139
13.57.26	P11 start	3.1kft	344	18°42'/76°0'	Descend to 300ft below cloud base.
[13.08	2hr left]				

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...419. Date 12/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER. Page 6 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13:56:10	P11 ↓	2.5kft	346	18°42'/76°0'	CB = 2SD 923mb 9.37°/11.01° 3m/s/138°
13:56:39	P11end	2.1kft	277	18°36'/76°0'	2200ft, 937mb 10.80°/10.85° 4m/s/152
					M4 - Wind peaks with some upward velocity
14:01:12	R12 start	2.1kft	103	18°42'/76°0'	2200ft 937mb 11.01°/10.64° 5m/s/100°
					Core cloud - 2 drops / liter
					2DS -
					AMS nothing significant...
					Core cloud - 70 pcasp
					CN1 pcasp = 150-200 cm ³ CPC ~600
					FAMM CPC 400 cm ³ ↕ 400
					CEN 85/400 @ 0.1%
					vACE - 4mill 2mill chl, 2 - huh!
					SMPS - monomodal - peak ~ 120 nm
					not much < 20-30 nm
				M3 report	- Only thing changed < 0.2°C SST
14:11:45	RB	2.1kft	129	19°6'/75°30'	all else constant - small ocean currents -
14:21:39	R12°/R2	2.1kft	129	19°24'/75°0'	2200ft → 500ft now 937mb 10.54°/10.55° 4m/s/119°
14:26:31	P12end	0.1kft	308	19°24'/75°0'	500ft / 1013mb 16.9°/12.24° 3m/s/169°
14:26 ⁽⁴³⁾	R13 start				100ft ~ 16.67°/11.91° 2m/s/160°
				M4 reports	- Not well mixed - like M3 reported !!
					980mb - burst from relative humidity and in
					small supercooled at 980mb
					suspect lower layer BL.
					Do 228 - run on GPU for an hour - ARSF
					team - End flg for an hour.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...419 Date 12/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 7 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14.35.11	RB	100ft/0ft	304	19°6'/75°30'	RB fly past - spike on P _{ly} mist @ 100ft spikes on CPC's (16.75°/11.55° 1012mb 4/190) might be - diff slightly SO ₄ ↑ O ₃ ↓ SO ₄ 2 μg/m ³ ; O ₃ 0.6 (AMS) SMPS - mostly nmo modal - slight shift to larger sizes 150nm maybe slightly smaller Core cloud PCASP ~ 90 cm ⁻³ CY1 (PCASP) 12 cm ⁻³ CPC = 400 cm ⁻³ AMS CCN - 290-80/400
14.43.00					Sea Salt on Windscreen
14.44.56	RB _{end} / PB _{start}	100ft/0ft	305	18°42'/75°54'	100ft/1012mb 16.91°/11.95° S _{ms} /162°
14.47.44	PB3	2.7kt	174	18°42'/76°0'	CB on PB 9.57°/10.32° S _{ms} /122°
14.48.50	PB3	3.7kt	115	18°42'/76°00'	CT 3900ft/682mb 7.12°/9.76° S _{ms} /89° TLC profile small increase at 950mb (145) superadiabatic on way down - small increase
14.49.37	PB3	4.4kt	125	18°42'/76°00'	on way up ↑ over R1 new 860mb 19.21°/19.78°
14.42.0					above RB new) ???
		4.8kt			entering pollution at 4800 ft
				(M4)	D ₂₂₈ short i/c runs with 146 tomorrow am now
		6.0kt			through a little O ₃ layer 6.0kt all correlates with CO ↑ as we go
14.54.50	PB3				GI :-
					layer 4500 → 10000 out of pollution
14.55.52	PB _{end} / PK _{start}	9.9kt	126	19.0°/75.7°	10000ft

14.56.05 PK+ 9.9kt 125 19°0'/75°36' 698mb 14.51°/-25.79° 1km/s/105°

end run
14.45

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴¹⁹ Date^{12/11/08} Name^{KN BOWER} Page⁸ of¹¹

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
15:00.37	P14 ^{end} /R14	5.9kft	129	19°12'/75°24'	6000ft. / 813mb 18.51°/31.62° 3m/s/120°
15:08.24	R14 ^{end}	5.9kft	126	19°24'/75°0'	6000ft / 813mb 19.86/-30.37 5m/s/92°
					Will do a run in CT - turbulence / turbulence
^{6000ft} 15:08.24	R14 ^{end}	5.9kft		Slide 31	check - Probe down to CT....
15:09.45	P14 st ↓	5.9kft	136	19°30'/74°54'	813mb / 6000ft 20.01°/-30.22° 5m/s/103°
					Remnant - entered wind vortices at 10
15:12.01	R14/R15	3.9kft	203	19°30'/74°54'	4000ft CT, 877mb 16.64°/-17.05° 3/212°
^{50ft ↓} 15:14.27	R15	3.8kft	308	19°24'/75°6'	dropped to get into CT properly 880mb 9.57°/-5.12°C
^{50ft ↓} 15:16.11	R15	3.8kft	307	19°15'/75°12'	dropped to get into CT again 880mb 10.57°/-0.13°C
15:21.52	R15 ^{end} /P16	3.8kft	309	19°06'/75°30'	W = -1 to 2 m/s ↑ .. 880mb 6.92°/9.81° 2m/s/113°
15:23.39	P16	2.9kft	56	19°0'/75°24'	PB 2500ft diffuse 927mb 9.52°/10.71° 2m/s/63°
15:27.58	P16/P17	0kft	62	18°54'/75°12'	50ft heading out to GI / v 1013mb 17.26°/12.82°
					lobit satellite picture - which shows
					Point Golf - right on edge of coastal decrease
					port - so possibly will not have enough cloud
					for the intercomparison with GI.
15:31.48	P17	4.0kft	61	18°48'/75°0'	CT 3900ft 16.95°/6.88° 874mb 1m/s/220°
15:32.73	P17 ^{end}	4.4kft	60	18°42'/74°54'	AMS - (CN → 0.2% _{now} , 4500ft/860mb
15:36.03	Transit	4.4kft	56	18°36'/74°42'	860mb 18.89°/-23.94°C 1m/s/32°
15:40.41	Descent	4.2kft	58	18°30'/74°30'	Slight ↑ ^{O₂} 35 ppb - anticorrelated with ...
15:41.13	Descent	3.7kft	94	18°30'/74°24'	CT 3500ft on descent to 110 level. 883mb.
15:41.38	Descent	3.4kft	94	18°30'/74°24'	893mb 8.39°/-0.24°C 2m/s/84°
					GI varying between 3400-3700' to stay at cloud
					Cloud physics - here:-
					CBP 0-300 cm ⁻³
					FSSP 0-500 cm ⁻³
					dryfl occasional 75µm in size

(= 16.5 - 74 W)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 491 Date 12/11/08..... Name KN BOWER..... Page 9 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
15 41 13	Desc	3.7	94	18°30'/74°24'	853 mb 10.26/-26.23° 3 m/s/91°
15.41 36	Desc	3.4	94	18°30'/74°24'	873 mb 8.39/-0.24° 2 m/s/84°
15.43 18	Desc	3.5	94	18°30'/74°18'	890 mb 7.51/8.69° 3 m/s/69°
15.44 05	Desc	3.4kt	92	18°30'/74°12'	Cloud just burning off - dropped another 50ft
15.51 39	Rubc / P15	3.3kt	91	18°30'/73°48'	↓ to 1000ft for 1st run. 869 _{9.0} 9.04/9.01° (1014 not bad as QNH)
15.55.04	P15 / R17	1kt	94	18°30'/73°30'	1000ft run / 976 mb 15.05/11.93° 2 m/s/153° AMS 5µg SO ₄ , 0.7µg Org CPC ~ 700-650 cm ⁻³ CCN 250-275 on 0.2% PCASO 150 cm ⁻³ M4 meson CNI PCASO 240 cm ⁻³ CPC 650 cm ⁻³ VACE VCASE ----
				MS	Ocean Eddy at 15ms 160nm
16 05 05	R17 / P20	1000/0.9kt	93	18°30'/73°0'	977 mb 15.67/11.16°C 1 m/s/99°
16 09. 10	P20 / R18	4.4kt	85	18°30'/72°42'	4500ft/861 m 18.53/3.92° (CB was ~ 30kt)
16.07.46	P20	3.2kt	90	18°30'/72°48'	CT was at 3300/898 mb 12.65/8.42° (but) AMS CPC counts slightly higher at this level than at 1000ft CCN = 200 (0.2%) CPC 900 cm ⁻³ (below cloud 250 particles / 650 cm ⁻³)
	P20 cont.	4.4kt			SMPS - definite - poss bimodal. SS rim diameter smaller.
16.13	R18				PCASO - 50 cm 2ds 3 cm ⁻³ / smaller 600nm

CL
BC
1000ft
Leg 1 - S 16 30.74 W 074 26.61
Leg 2 - S 18 31.84 73 30.93

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 419 Date 12/11/08 Name KN BOWER Page 10 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					SO ₄ loadings have decreased - less Acc mode - more 100nm and less particles - less in milk ↓ in CN #
16.19.09	P16/P21	4.4kl	88	18°24'/72°6'	4500ft / 860mb 19.8°/1.58°C 6m/s/355° (Start a Sawtooth profile down to 50ft) Core Chem - variation in O ₃ 12-22ppt (CO ₂ too)
16.25.21	P21/022	0kl	89°	18°24'/71°42'	50ft/1010mb 18.92°/13.06°C 1m/s/218° AMS 2000ft - SO no change on Ac/pub high SO ₄ - lower total CPC higher CN → reduction in ... ratio CPC counts
16.30.50	P22/023	4.8kl	89	18°30'/71°24'	846mb 20.91°/-17.62° 4m/s/2° sub 100nm mode - slightly higher CPC ↓ CN G1 - during same as us run (sawtoothing) just above C7 - distinct layer - strong W component - 50 mbar thick - strong 10kt N NW → N.
16.32.12	P23	3.3kl	90°	18°30'/71°12'	3400' (CT) 14.77°/-6.04°C 2m/s/311°
16.33.49	P23	2.8kl	89°	18°30'/71°12'	CB - but very very murky - hazy (1015 good QNH)
16.36.48	P23				Fishing Boat below

Instrumentation B419.

Memos - US

PCASP - same as usual.

1 hard disc

CVI - fine

Neph - -

SWS - -

ACES - OK

VALL - PCASP scanned - no useful data.

Corechem - no problems.

ZDS - CAPS ✓✓

AMS ✓

Sms ✓

Buck quantity OK

Ron Braun - decimal position - ?? wrong

saw him on radar ahead as headed to original posⁿ 1st

Fam 710 low level cut - 80 W

multiple heights - high level return.

Do concern as forleg - right up - to low level

Fly cut again with (130) 710

Mission Scientist's Log

M.S.2 -

Flight No B.149 Date 12/11/08 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
1130					to ARICA, v. light fc. wind.
113542		5600			over cloud now.
—					RMB 19 4.9'S 75° 32.3'W
—					157deg @ 5.3kt.
120727		3800			tops.
		3100			base.
—					RMB tops 1100m base 750m
—					a little drizzle but not too f.c.
122501	P6	2900			
—					CDP 270 12µm 15L-1 2DC MF 420 12-13µm 200µm.
122547	R6	3			CAS 500-600µm
—					RMB 19 27.36' 75 19.79'
		4100			tops
					P7 cooler & moister than P6.
1256					167 / 3ms ⁻¹ no whitecap
125718		100			about P9 - end R7.
130222		3500			R8 CDP 200 20µm MF 250 20µm
					CAS 450
131209		"			o/h RMB
1320					LWC v. steady along run.
132202		"			end R8 & prof above.
		3900			tops.
133526					R10 (& R9) reverse latg legs for wind dir.
133800		3200	304		R11 start. s-v.
					CDP 160 16-17µm 2DC 30L-1 MF 230 16 " 250µm.

20-400' water.

Mission Scientist's Log

M.S. 2.
3

Flight No B. 419

Date 12/11/08

Name

Page 2 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
1346		3200			LWC very steady again.
134724					q/h RMB. slight lwc peak here.
—					RMB reports steady drizzle
135655		2500			end R11 no drizzle on W-band base
140112		2			start R12 just ocean drizzle.
—					CU, 150-200 PEARP 600 CRC
1411					note E wind component changing most between headings.
—					SMPS pke 120 nm.
—					runs are roughly alongwind
—					so this consistent with AoS error
1420					AoA cal, poss slight effect comp. to earlier flights
142140		2200			end 12 - prof. to 50'
—					still 1deg AoS effect on Horace
142633		100ft	309		run 13. Profile shows spc. layer with higher Q _w
—					PEARP 90 - poss OK?
—					CU, PEARP 120 CRC 400
—					can 80-90 / 120 @ 0.1%
1443					sea salt on screen.
144457		1			end 13 e prof. drizzle slightly higher winds with few whitecaps
—					
—					

14467

3900 tops.

Prof. 13 is well-mixed mostly, but only up to ~2-300 below cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No B. 419

 Date 12/11/08

 Name G. ALLEN

 Page 1 of 5

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
10:50	'	0	'	'	Surface conditions: 1008 mb, T = 21°C, DP = 8.2°C. Clear sky. Can see Sc deck out to sea on horizon. Sat pic shows solid Sc deck over area of ops.
11:30					T/O toward Romeo
11:33					900 mb = inversion. Top of cloud at 3300 ft. CB = 60 pftV just above cloud at 4000 ft.
11:35	R1	6000ft	261°	70°48'W	
11:40	P2b	5000ft	261°		Down to 5000ft. 3500ft = CTH CB = 2700ft. 1004.
11:46	R2	800ft		71°24.18°S	Intercomp run 1
11:50	P3a	3200ft			
11:55	R3	3300ft			In-cloud. 18°36'S. 71°54'W. 12:47z -RV at RHB. CTH = 3600ft.
12:01	R4	4600ft			5-min run.
12:05	P5b				Sea ball - 50ft to 500ft for 10-min run - CB = 3800, 3100ft.
12:12	R5	500ft			10-min run. RHB reports (CB = 750m, CTH = 1100m)
12:25	R6	3500ft			10-min.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...419 Date 12/11/08 Name G. Allen Page 2 of 5

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12:26		3500ft			CDP = 270, D _{in} = 12μm - 13μm. FSSP = 420-450, Core = . D _{in} = 15/litre drizzle → 200μm ZDS - same, 500-600/cc. 19°27.36', 75.19.179°W
12:36					CTH = 4100ft.
12:38	P86	500ft			CTH = 4000ft. Core check repeating NA spikes but there are incorrect, similar to bad data seen before.
12:47	R7	100ft			10. RV - with RHB 10 mi run. at 100ft 076°00.13'W R2 = 19°29.17' W 075°01.73'W RHB: 11°28.746'S W 075°073.09W
12:57	P97				CB = 2800ft CTH = ?
13:01	R8	3500ft	127°	75°, 19°18'S	Tn-cloud run at 3500ft 20 min. Drizzle - 200μm. ZDS. CAS = 450/cc sizes 15-70μm. 0.7-0.9 LWC.
13:22	P105	4900ft			1000ft above cloud: 3900ft CTH. 5-mi reciprocal.
13:25					CO, O ₃ spikes at 4800ft. Bottom of layer change: CO → 70ppbv. O ₃ > 15 → 40ppbv (3x increase).

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...4A Date 12/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 3 of 5

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13:38	R11	3200ft	308°	19°55'75"W	20-mi cloud run - Nox → 0 ppbv Above cloud suggesting that Nox is real below cloud. Dia = 16µm - FSSP = 230/cc, 16µm. Drizzle = 30/liter - 250µm - CA = 400/cc - 14-15µm dia - LWC = 0.3
13:47	R11	19°6'75"30"	308°	3200ft -	over haul 13:47L (RHB) AMS reports SO ₂ reduction at 13:47L
13:57	P11W	2200ft			CB = 2500ft -
13:59	R12	2200ft			
14:00	R12	2200ft	119°	2200ft	Reversal of wind dir ^c correlated by increase in W-wind. 1-3 µg m ⁻³ SO ₄ - AMS. SMPS - 120 nm. No change in anything (!) across this run. Aerosol, Chem etc all constant.
14:22	P12L	50ft	308°	19°30', 75°W	Thermos probe down to 50 ft, then up to 100 ft. No change on run, but AMS reports up to 2 2 µg m ⁻³ SO ₄ on run - Slightly more than at 2200ft -
14:35			308°		RHB overpass time.
14:44	P13A	10000ft -			2700ft CB - 3900ft CTH. Pollution layer at 4400ft. All the way up to 10000ft CO peaks at 73 ppbv, O ₂ → 40 ppbv

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 419 Date 12/11/05 Name G. ALLEN Page 4 of 5

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14:55		10000ft	177°		Pollution layer all the way to 10000ft before returning to background levels.
15:01	R14	6000ft			Correlation between E-wind and CO
15:15	R15	3850ft			Turbulence measurements.
15:18	R15	3700	308°		Peaks up to -1ms ⁻¹ or -2ms ⁻¹
					15:21 (over RHB) -
15:22	P16↑				Move toward GOLF.
					CB=2500ft - (TH=3900ft)
15:40	R16	3600ft	60°		In-cloud run first due to coastal clearance.
		4300ft		18°36' 74°42'	Entering CO layer at pos.
15:46	R16	3450ft	92°	18°30' 74°30'	CO → 62 ppb, O ₃ → 40 ppbv.
					COP = 0-300 - diam 10µm. FSSP-500
					10µm. S/liter detected 75µm.
					Very difficult to stay in cloud.
					Right on edge of coastal light area.
					Thin, broken cloud.
15:52	P19↓	1000ft	92°	18°50' 73°42' W	Sub-cloud aerosol run (10 min)
					AMS: 5µg SO ₄ 0.7µg O ₃
					CPC - 700/cc. CCN 250→2500
					0.2% - from
					Tephi shows offset on profile ascent
16:05					in-line with increasing SST seen by Hermann -

Chemistry Log

Date: 12/11/08

Flight: B419

Operator: KFT

Preflight CO, O₃, NO_x, SO₂ operated.

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases			
1	☒ CO2/Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	110
2	☒ CO2/Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	
3	☒ CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
4	☒ CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	40
5	☒ Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
6	☒ Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	15
Flows			
7	☒ Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels	
8	☒ NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	☒ NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	☒ CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	☒ CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar	
12	☒ CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
Zeros			
13	☒ Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	☒ NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	☒ CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	
Other			
16	☒ Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
17	☒ HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
18	☒ CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	Manual valve turns
<i>CO clock checked.</i>			
TDLAS			
19	☒ 230V	230V power breakers on	
20	☒ 28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
21	☒ Laptop	On and software working	
22	☒ Data	Being saved to correct directories	
Post Flight			
Switch off			
1	☒ CO	Switch off instrument	
2	☒ Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	☒ NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	☒ Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	☒ Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
Gases (note pressures)			
6	☒ CO2/Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	160
7	☒ CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	40
8	☒ Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	8
<i>If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling</i>			
Driers			
9	☒ Small drier	Change if spent	
10	☒ Large drier	Change if spent	
TDLAS			
11	☒ Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	☒ Laptop	Shut down	
13	☒ Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
Log			
14	☒ Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	☒ Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	☒ TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

B419. In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
11:30	Taxy	93.34	301	28093	38.79	7.51
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)

CO 'Cal'

Flight level	Zero Start	Zero End	Counts (Hz)	Span Start	Span End	Conc. Range	Counts range	Sensitivity	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities
3400FT.	12:25	-2ppb	27700	12:26		519	76800				7.53	38.48	115kH ₂
4800FT	13:29	-4ppb.	27700	13:30		518	76300				7.52	38.16	112kH ₂
3900FT.	15:12	-6ppb	27500	15:13		516	76200				7.53	38.13	112kH ₂
4400FT	16:09	-6ppb	27300			512	75900				7.53	38.46	114kH ₂
Taxy	16:53	-4ppb	27600			518	76000				7.53	38.96	114kH ₂

	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)

In flight comments

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 419

Date: 12/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:32:45	40	0.07	2													FL030	
11:33:35	110	0.07														FL040	
11:35:07	20	0.07														FL050	
11:36:30	20	0.07														End of P & Start Run @ FL060	
11:40:11	10	0.07														End of Run 1 & Start P2	
11:41:59	20	0.07														FL040	
11:43:15	70	0.12														FL030	
11:44:22	150	0.12	153													FL020	
11:45:30	170	0.12														FL010	
11:46:27																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2 @ 500'	
11:47:00	170	0.07														CDP to manual value	
11:49:00	200	0.07															
11:51:30																End of Run 2 & Start P3	
11:52:17	90	0.07														FL010	
11:53:30	80	0.07														FL020	
11:54:57	60	0.08	214			6		400	10			0.2	200	10	0.1	12	End of P3 & Start Run 3 @ 3300'
11:57:00	70	0.11	416			10	100	270	11			0.2	200	11	0.1	12	
11:59:00	65	0.12	626			3	100	325	12			0.2	200	11	0.1	12	
12:00:14																	End of Run & Start P4
12:01:00	20	0.07	737														
12:03:00	5	0.07															
12:05:00	10	0.07															
12:06:36																	End of Run & Start P5
12:07:11	5	0.07															FL040
12:08:12	5	0.07															FL030
12:09:13	90	0.07	823														FL020
12:10:22	100	0.07															FL010
12:11:46																	End of P & Start Run 5 @ 500'
12:12:00	130	0.07															
12:14:00	140	0.07															
12:16:00	220	0.07															
12:18:00	200	0.07															
12:20:00	160	0.07															
12:22:18																	End of Run & Start P6
12:22:57	190	0.07	824														FL010
12:24:04	140	0.07															FL020
12:25:42																	End of P & Start Run 6 @ 3500'
12:26:00	60	0.15	1093			15	125	400	12			0.3	250	13	0.3	12	
12:29:00	130	0.16	1415			10	125	600	14			0.45	300	14	0.4	12	
12:31:00			FAIL														
12:32:00	90	0.16	97			6	100	700	14			0.4	350	14	0.35	12	
12:34:00	130	0.16	500			20	100	600	15			0.45	300	14	0.40	12	
12:36:06																	End of Run & Start P7

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.6V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.9CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 419

Date: 12/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
12:37:46	10	0.07														End of P7 & Start P8 @ FL050	
12:38:44	5	0.07	1024													FL040	
12:39:49	130	0.18	1198			25	175	300	18			0.8	200	18	0.6	FL030	
12:42:02	180	0.08	1216													FL010	
12:44:30	130	0.07														End of P @ 50'	
12:44:40																Start Run 7 @ 100'	
12:45:00	110	0.07															
12:47:00	60	0.07															
12:49:00	80	0.07															
12:51:00	65	0.07	1217														
12:53:00	65	0.07															
12:57:18																End of Run & Start P9	
12:58:34	110	0.07														FL010	
12:59:40	90	0.07														FL020	
13:00:55																End of P @ FL034	
13:02:24																Start Run 8 @ FL034	
13:03:00	170	0.17	1635			25	125	280	18			0.5	200	19	0.6	12	
13:05:00	180	0.18	1964			45	175	300	18			0.6	200	19	0.6	1	
13:07:00	180	0.19	2293			20	225	225	18			0.6	190	19	0.6	1	
13:09:00	150	0.18	2540			15	200	250	19			0.55	190	20	0.6	1	
13:11:00	130	0.18	2746			20	100	275	19			0.5	190	20	0.7	12	
13:13:00	160	0.18	3100			15	100	350	19			0.6	210	20	0.8	12	
13:15:00	180	0.19	3427			16	150	260	18			0.55	200	20	0.6	1	
13:17:00	170	0.19	3609			35	250	220	19			0.55	170	20	0.6	1	
13:19:00	160	0.18	3857			35	200	270	19			0.5	170	19	0.6	1	
13:22:00																End of Run & Start P10	
13:23:50																End of P10 & Start Run 9 @ 4800'	
13:24:00	2	0.07															
13:30:27																End of Run 9 & Start Run 10 @ 4800'	
13:35:32																End of Run 10	
13:38:03																Start Run 11 @ 3200'	
13:39:00	100	0.19	4562			20	200	250	17			0.4	200	15	0.35	1	
13:41:00	70	0.19	4879			35	200	220	16			0.35	160	16	0.35	1	
13:43:00	90	0.19	5109			35	225	240	17			0.3	160	16	0.4	1	
13:47:00	120	0.20	5543			30	200	270	17			0.3	160	16	0.35	1	
13:49:00	80	0.19	5738			35	200	220	17			0.3	170	16	0.35	1	
13:51:00	100	0.17	5964			40	200	260	16			0.3	170	16	0.35	1	
13:53:00	100	0.18	6174			30	200	250	17			0.3	170	16	0.35	1	
13:55:00	75	0.18	6394			5	275	250	16			0.2	160	15	0.3	1	
13:56:55																End of Run	
13:57:32																Start P11 from 3200'	
13:58:42																End of P @ 2200'	
14:01:13																Start Run 12 @ 2200'	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.6V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.9CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 419

Date: 12/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
14:02:00	70	0.07	6685			2											
14:04:00	90	0.07				3	250									1	
14:06:00	100	0.07															
14:08:00	70	0.07				2	250									1	
14:10:00	70	0.07				2	300									1	
14:12:00	80	0.07				2	200									1	
14:14:00	80	0.07	6686			1	200									1	
14:16:00	100	0.07				3	250									1	
14:18:00	120	0.07	6687			1	225									1	
14:20:00	100	0.07				3	250									1	
14:21:41																	
14:22:03	130	0.07															
14:23:55	110	0.07															
14:26:33	150	0.07															
14:26:45																	
14:27:00	100	0.07															
14:29:00	120	0.07															
14:31:00	90	0.07															
14:33:00	90	0.07	6688														
14:35:00	370	0.07															
14:37:00	90	0.07															
14:39:00	100	0.07															
14:41:00	70	0.07															
14:43:00	110	0.07															
14:45:02																	
14:46:01	65	0.07	6689														
14:47:00	65	0.07				3	250									1	
14:48:07	36	0.09	6724			50	225	260	15			0.45	150	16	0.3	1	
14:49:15	10	0.07	6785														
14:50:18	10	0.06															
14:51:30	5	0.07	6786														
14:52:35	2	0.07															
14:54:54	2	0.07	6866														
14:55:55	2	0.07															
14:57:15	5	0.07															
14:58:18	5	0.07															
14:59:24	2	0.07															
15:00:39																	
15:01:00	2	0.07															
15:03:00	2	0.07															
15:05:00	2	0.07															
15:07:00	2	0.07															
15:08:26																	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.6V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.9CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 419

Date: 12/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
15:09:47																Start Profile 15	
15:11:49	3	0.06														FL040	
15:12:01																Start Run 15 @ FL038	
15:14:00	3	0.07															
15:16:00	50	0.07	6889			10	75	100	19			0.6	150	19	0.5	12	
15:18:00	75	0.17	7037			25	150	170	18			0.5	140	20	0.45	1	
15:20:00	90	0.17	7230			50	175	160	18			0.5	130	21	0.45	1	
15:21:54																End of Run & Start P16	
15:22:51	65	0.08	7492			20	200	220	12			0.25	140	12	0.3	1	
15:24:12	90	0.07	7508			2	200									FL030	
15:25:36	100	0.07	7508													FL020	
15:28:00	100	0.07														FL010	
15:29:09	75	0.07														End of P16 & Start P17 @ 50'	
15:30:11	60	0.07														FL010	
15:30:59	60	0.07														FL020	
15:31:50	2	0.06														FL030	
15:32:26	2	0.09														FL040	
15:40:38																End of P @ 4500'	
15:41:49																Start P18	
15:42:00	10	0.08	7654					350	10			0.3	200	10	0.05	End of P18 & Start Run 16 @ 3800'	
15:44:00	60	0.08	7764			7	75	200	12			0.1	180	11	0.1		
15:46:00	100	0.07															
15:48:00	100	0.08	7879			1		300	10			0.05	200	10	0.05		
15:50:00	50	0.07	7881														
15:51:41																End of Run & Start P19	
15:52:12	200	0.07														FL030	
15:53:30	150	0.07	7882													FL020	
15:55:07																End of P19 & Start Run 17 @ 1000'	
15:56:00	190	0.07															
15:58:00	180	0.07															
16:00:00	180	0.07															
16:02:00	150	0.07	8002														
16:04:00	100	0.07															
16:05:11																End of Run & Start P20	
16:06:19	80	0.07														FL020	
16:07:29	50	0.08	8027													FL030	
16:08:38	20	0.08														FL040	
16:09:10																End of P & Start Run 16 @ FL044	
16:10:00	60	0.08															
16:12:00	40	0.07	8032														
16:14:00	50	0.07															
16:16:00	25	0.07															
16:18:00	5	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2V	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.6V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.9CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

P.S.A.P. Log

Flight No. **B419**

Date 12/11/2008

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GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$	Ph_det levels	Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time: done 074920Z	New filter Tr = 1.000 done	Set to 3.0 lpm: N/A			Ave =30 s	←-Preflight
11:45	.990				r2	pump on
11:53	.988				p3	pump off
12:01	.994				r4	pump on
12:06	.993					pump off
12:09	.985					pump on
12:22	.982				p6	pump off
12:41	.982				p8	pump on
r7					r7 100ft	pump on
12:57	.978				p9	pump off
13:22	.979				p10	pump on
13:37	.981				r10	pump off
13:58	.977				p11	pump on
14:47	.968				p13	pump off
14:54	.981				p13	pump on
15:16	.970				r15	pump off, maybe bit late, cloud top run already started
15:24	.966				p16	pump on
15:40	.980??					pump off
15:52	.965				p19	pump on
16:05	.960					pump off
16:10	.966					pump on
16:40						pump on off
16:59	.953				on ground	

Size	#	charged	Flight/Date	Discharged	Comments
10 1	1 2 }	KNB 11/11	B419 12/11	12/11 KNB	
10 1	3 4 }	KNB 11/11	B419 12/11	12/11 KNB	
10 1	7 8 }	KNB 11/11	B419 12/11	12/11 KNB	
10 1	10 69 }	KNB 11/11	B419 12/11	12/11 KNB	
10 1	31 23 }	KNB 11/11	B419 12/11	12/11 KNB	Wet
10 1	33 40 }	KNB 11/11	B419 12/11	12/11 KNB	

Filter #	Loc ^N	Ton	ToFF	RUN	TOTAL VOL	
3, 4, 49	U	12:17	12:23	R5	322	-
10, 69, 140	U	12:48	12:57	R7	530	< post Run Down before 5min filter drying time
1, 2, 117	U	14:04	14:46	R112 R13	2277	- just below CB
33, 40, -	U	15:02	15:09	R14	257	-
21, 20 83	U	15:56	16:05	R17	504	-
7 8 152	U	16:10	16:38		2	BLANK

CVI log

11/12/08 10:07:20 AM
11/12/08 10:07:24 AM
11/12/08 10:07:29 AM
11/12/08 10:07:49 AM change the display
11/12/08 10:07:58 AM set up counterflow to dry the circuit
11/12/08 10:45:18 AM first lyman zero
11/12/08 10:45:29 AM lyman has just been turned on
11/12/08 10:45:41 AM LyI0=0.64
11/12/08 10:48:32 AM LyI0=0.64
11/12/08 10:48:39 AM LyI0=0.64
11/12/08 10:48:42 AM LyI0=0.64
11/12/08 10:48:45 AM LyI0=0.64
11/12/08 10:50:25 AM LyI0=1.82
11/12/08 10:57:36 AM LyI0=19.2
11/12/08 10:58:03 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 10:58:12 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 10:59:51 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 10:59:56 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 10:59:59 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:00:05 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:00:07 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:00:10 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:03:01 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:03:05 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:03:08 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:03:11 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:03:19 AM increase dilution factor, zero lyman alpha
11/12/08 11:36:41 AM final lyman zero
11/12/08 11:36:48 AM lyman to sample
11/12/08 11:40:20 AM keep counterflow on until below cloud
11/12/08 11:40:23 AM keep counterflow on until below cloud
11/12/08 11:40:29 AM keep counterflow on until below cloud
11/12/08 11:40:44 AM keep counterflow on until below cloud
11/12/08 11:41:34 AM keep counterflow on until below cloud
11/12/08 11:42:24 AM can't seem to get a decent zero on anymore
11/12/08 11:43:05 AM can't seem to get a decent zero on anymore
11/12/08 11:43:13 AM can't seem to get a decent zero on anymore
11/12/08 11:46:27 AM cvi into zerosol mode
11/12/08 11:47:06 AM cvi into zerosol mode
11/12/08 11:50:02 AM tip is very warm 40deg
11/12/08 11:52:32 AM tip is very warm 40deg
11/12/08 11:54:47 AM in counterflow cloud thin ams on counterflow
11/12/08 11:56:23 AM in counterflow cloud thin ams on counterflow
11/12/08 11:56:31 AM in counterflow cloud thin ams on counterflow
11/12/08 11:56:38 AM in counterflow cloud thin ams on counterflow
11/12/08 11:56:51 AM in counterflow cloud thin ams on counterflow
11/12/08 11:56:57 AM in counterflow cloud thin ams on counterflow
11/12/08 11:57:00 AM in counterflow cloud thin ams on counterflow
11/12/08 12:01:14 PM back to aerosol mode now
11/12/08 12:01:26 PM ams says cvi worked well on that run
11/12/08 12:03:42 PM ams says cvi worked well on that run
11/12/08 12:03:44 PM ams says cvi worked well on that run
11/12/08 12:04:28 PM ams says cvi worked well on that run
11/12/08 12:06:45 PM turn lyman to reference air for cloud passage
11/12/08 12:09:14 PM counterflow is off, turn lyman back to sample plenum air
11/12/08 12:13:12 PM sub cloud aerosol - cpc=640, cnc-cpc=612
11/12/08 12:24:06 PM 1000ft below, into counterflow mode
11/12/08 12:24:13 PM 1000ft below, into counterflow mode
11/12/08 12:24:18 PM 1000ft below, into counterflow mode
11/12/08 12:26:09 PM 1000ft below, into counterflow mode
11/12/08 12:28:48 PM 1000ft below, into counterflow mode
11/12/08 12:32:16 PM leave in counterflow mode above cloud to see if we get a zero or not - cut the ams flow if needed
11/12/08 12:35:04 PM plenum pressure is 80mb higher than ambient
11/12/08 12:36:27 PM plenum pressure is 80mb higher than ambient
11/12/08 12:36:30 PM ams gone
11/12/08 12:36:33 PM cloud top

11/12/08 12:37:48 PM still can't get a zero
11/12/08 12:38:20 PM still can't get a zero
11/12/08 12:38:44 PM might be attitude dependant, or pressure dependant
11/12/08 12:40:18 PM below cloud, into aerosol mode
11/12/08 12:40:33 PM still seeing some drizzle
11/12/08 12:41:52 PM out of drizzle now
11/12/08 12:41:59 PM use 2dc in the processing?
11/12/08 12:42:23 PM use 2dc in the processing?
11/12/08 12:42:54 PM use 2dc in the processing?
11/12/08 12:43:07 PM use 2dc in the processing?
11/12/08 12:59:50 PM into cvi mode
11/12/08 1:00:00 PM well mixed clean boundary layer
11/12/08 1:00:12 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:01:48 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:01:53 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:01:56 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:03:36 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:12:24 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:12:29 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:15:57 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:16:02 PM into cloud
11/12/08 1:16:42 PM very low pcasp counts
11/12/08 1:16:55 PM very high cpc counts
11/12/08 1:17:12 PM strange blip halfway throught the run, a step change
11/12/08 1:22:53 PM into aerosol mode for above cloud legs
11/12/08 1:23:06 PM will do reciprocal slr for wind cal
11/12/08 1:33:09 PM try and get a zero again
11/12/08 1:34:16 PM just about got a zero
11/12/08 1:37:13 PM are we getting drizzle shattering?
11/12/08 1:40:21 PM are we getting drizzle shattering?
11/12/08 1:46:33 PM are we getting drizzle shattering?
11/12/08 1:47:59 PM gettung bumpy, lwc increasing
11/12/08 1:48:05 PM drop conc increasing
11/12/08 1:55:31 PM blip may be when the aircraft passed over the ron brown,
simililar signals from others, including a drop, a DROP in so2 from ams,
increase in lwc from others,
11/12/08 1:56:15 PM cloud base very smooth indicTING weak large scale motions -
message from ron brown
11/12/08 1:58:02 PM ams off
11/12/08 1:58:14 PM cvi into aerosol mode at cloud base 2.5kft
11/12/08 1:58:59 PM 300ft below cloud base leg
11/12/08 1:59:29 PM 300ft below cloud base leg
11/12/08 1:59:38 PM 300ft below cloud base leg
11/12/08 1:59:41 PM 300ft below cloud base leg
11/12/08 2:00:02 PM 300ft below cloud base leg
11/12/08 2:00:05 PM 300ft below cloud base leg
11/12/08 2:00:52 PM wind peak with upward velocity. we see an increase in cpc counts
11/12/08 2:01:32 PM drizzle
11/12/08 2:02:47 PM 1-3 mu g of sulphate today
11/12/08 2:03:40 PM 1-3 mu g of sulphate today
11/12/08 2:03:46 PM 1-3 mu g of sulphate today
11/12/08 2:03:48 PM 1-3 mu g of sulphate today
11/12/08 2:04:11 PM 1-3 mu g of sulphate today
11/12/08 2:04:21 PM 1-3 mu g of sulphate today
11/12/08 2:08:11 PM LyI0=1.95
11/12/08 2:10:17 PM very well mixed day
11/12/08 2:12:41 PM smps - mono modal accumulation mode aerosol
11/12/08 2:20:38 PM aerosol legs are mind-numbing
11/12/08 2:21:30 PM all aerosol and no cloud makes jack a...
11/12/08 2:23:07 PM banking now
11/12/08 2:23:14 PM cpc=cpc-cnc
11/12/08 2:23:36 PM cpc=cpc-cnc
11/12/08 2:23:40 PM cpc=cpc-cnc
11/12/08 2:29:21 PM cpc=cpc-not well mixed bl, break from adiabatic line, change in
mixing ratio, small adiabatic laye at 980, lower level bl here
11/12/08 2:35:43 PM cpc=cpc-not well mixed bl, break from adiabatic line, change in
mixing ratio, small adiabatic laye at 980, lower level bl here
11/12/08 2:35:46 PM cpc=cpc-not well mixed bl, break from adiabatic line, change in
mixing ratio, small adiabatic laye at 980, lower level bl here

11/12/08 2:36:40 PM bog spike from 500-2500 on cpcs as we pass the ron brown
11/12/08 2:38:48 PM bog spike from 500-2500 on cpcs as we pass the ron brown
11/12/08 2:41:12 PM how long does it take to mix a boudary layer given certain
profile , SST?
11/12/08 2:41:24 PM
11/12/08 2:46:42 PM
11/12/08 2:47:08 PM
11/12/08 2:47:12 PM
11/12/08 2:47:16 PM
11/12/08 2:47:19 PM
11/12/08 2:47:33 PM increase on cpc, pcasp - drizzle?
11/12/08 2:47:42 PM lyman oto reference
11/12/08 2:48:54 PM cloud top now 3.9kft
11/12/08 2:49:01 PM cloud top now 3.9kft
11/12/08 2:49:08 PM cloud top now 3.9kft
11/12/08 2:50:27 PM still banking
11/12/08 2:55:40 PM zero lyman
11/12/08 3:07:28 PM zero lyman
11/12/08 3:07:35 PM zero lyman
11/12/08 3:08:04 PM zero lyman again
11/12/08 3:08:30 PM lyman back to sample
11/12/08 3:10:39 PM into counterflow mode
11/12/08 3:10:46 PM ams into cvi
11/12/08 3:11:10 PM ams into cvi
11/12/08 3:11:16 PM ams into cvi
11/12/08 3:11:57 PM correlation east wind and CO
11/12/08 3:12:05 PM skimming cloud top at 4.0kft
11/12/08 3:14:37 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:14:41 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:15:03 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:15:05 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:15:10 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:15:17 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:15:43 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:16:51 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:16:56 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:17:08 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:17:53 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:19:27 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:22:38 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:22:42 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:22:47 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:22:52 PM ams onto rosemount, we stay in cvi
11/12/08 3:23:05 PM leave in cvi until well below cloud for any drizzle
11/12/08 3:23:32 PM
11/12/08 3:23:38 PM
11/12/08 3:24:30 PM
11/12/08 3:24:36 PM
11/12/08 3:27:55 PM into aerosol mode for climb
11/12/08 3:30:51 PM lyman to reference
11/12/08 3:32:07 PM lyman to cvi, inton cvi mode
11/12/08 3:32:19 PM ams onto cvi for cloud run
11/12/08 3:40:15 PM ams onto cvi for cloud run
11/12/08 3:40:45 PM ams onto cvi
11/12/08 3:40:48 PM ams onto cvi
11/12/08 3:41:26 PM cloud top 3.8, start of intercomparison with g1
11/12/08 3:41:34 PM hitting cloud base,
11/12/08 3:42:58 PM nudge to 3.5
11/12/08 3:47:40 PM nudge to 3.5
11/12/08 3:47:45 PM nudge to 3.5
11/12/08 3:47:51 PM nudge to 3.5
11/12/08 3:47:57 PM nudge to 3.5
11/12/08 3:52:17 PM descend to sub cloud aerosol leg level
11/12/08 3:52:23 PM turn off counterflow
11/12/08 3:54:55 PM turn off counterflow
11/12/08 3:54:59 PM turn off counterflow
11/12/08 4:05:17 PM start above cloud run
11/12/08 4:08:59 PM above bl run
11/12/08 4:11:57 PM above bl run

11/12/08 4:41:40 PM counterflow on to land

ARIES flight log

Flight: B419 page 1 of 2

Date: 12/Nov/2008 Operator(s): S. ROGERS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc/Notes: VOCALS

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
10 48	On the ground						Power on Ok.
10 55	"		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot line - script
11 30	TAKE OFF		-	C	71	31	-
11 36 19	6000ft?		NZ	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 30 sec. 8/8 seen below Ci above?
11 40 11	P2 ↓						6000ft → 500ft
11 46 47	500ft	N2	NZ	O	71	33	Nadir Long Run 3 min Below cloud but still a bit bumpy
11 51	P3 ↑		-	C	71	32	500ft → 3200ft
11 56 40	3200ft		CH	C	71	32	Cold Hot line In cloud
12 01 20	4600ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Above cloud 8/8 seen
12 06 39	P ↓		-	C	71	30	4600ft → 500ft
12 11 44	500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
12 22 29	↑		-	C	71	31	500ft → 3500ft
12 25 44	3500ft		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot line In cloud
12 31 58	"		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot line In cloud
12 44 38	100ft		N	C	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min Below cloud
12 50 18	"	240x1	Z	O	70	31	Zenith Passing "Run Brown"
12 52 23	"		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min EOR 1257
13 02 22	3500ft		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot line In cloud
13 08 15	"		CH	C	71	31	- " - - " -
13 23 36	4900ft		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min EOR 1328
13 30 37	"		Z	O	71	31	- " - Ci above? EOR 1335
13 36	↓						→ 3200ft
13 38 00	3200ft		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot line In cloud
13 55 00	"		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot line In cloud
13 58 43	2200ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min 300ft below cloud base
14 26 40	100ft		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min EOR 1421
14 36 33	100ft	120x1	Z	O	71	31	Zenith - shutter still closed at start.
14 37 40	"		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
14 45	100ft ↑		CH	C	71	30	Cold Hot line
15 00 39	6000 ft		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min 8/8 seen below
15 03 07	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min EOR 1508

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B419..**

Date 12/11/2008..

Operator's name JB.....

Page .1..... of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
11:43	p2					45		chiller on, Pre heater on
11:48	r2	500	14.1	52	84	10		
11:53:51	p3							run to short to complete cycle, leave low RH for cloud
12:01	r4	3000						run above cloud too short for cycle.
12:08			14	42	38	45		ready for 10 min 500ft ru
12:15	r5	500	14.7	45	69	15		
12:25	r6	3500	14.0	39	46			leave at low rh for 10 min cloud run
12:45	r7	100	14.3	45	45.9	45		
12:58	p9		14.0	44	84	12		go to low rh for cloud run past ron brown r8
13:18	r8		13.2	40	40	44		up to high rh for above cloud work.
13:29		4800						chiller off for profile to 10,000ft
13:30		4800						confusion! another run at same hight
13:39		3100	14.4	38	78	15		back down to low rh for cloud run. no more 10000ft?
14:01	r12	2100	14.3	45	44	45		
14:09	r12	2100	14.3	44	85	12		
14:15	r12	"	"	"	53	45		
14:26	r13	100	14.6	44	85	12		
14:43	r13	100	"	"	87	13		missed last log entry, rh to high
14:50	p13	5000						chiller off for 10000ft profle.
15:13	r15	3800	14.0	14.5	60	45		chiller on for run above cloud top

B419_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

09:34:28.76 --- - - - -
09:34:28.76 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:34:28.76 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:34:28.76 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B419
09:34:28.76 --- - - - -
09:34:34.13 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
09:34:36.89 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
09:34:37.45 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:34:40.75 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:34:45.31 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:34:49.43 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:34:49.98 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:34:50.80 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:34:51.92 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:34:54.10 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:34:57.80 SWS - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
09:34:57.81 SWS - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
09:34:59.24 USH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:35:01.67 USH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
09:35:01.68 USH - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
09:35:04.08 LSH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:35:07.54 LSH - - 200 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
09:35:07.55 LSH - - - 200 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
09:35:10.16 USH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
09:35:10.16 USH - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
09:35:13.44 SWS - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
09:35:13.44 SWS - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
09:35:14.62 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:35:14.62 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:35:14.63 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:35:46.23 SWS - - - - Idling
09:35:46.23 USH - - - - Idling
09:35:46.26 LSH - - - - Idling
09:35:48.23 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:35:48.23 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:35:48.24 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:35:49.66 SWS - - - - Idling
09:35:50.09 USH - - - - Idling
09:35:50.89 LSH - - - - Idling
09:35:57.94 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
09:35:59.60 SWS 169.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:46:17.51 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:17.51 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:17.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:21.20 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:46:21.25 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:46:21.28 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:46:21.83 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:46:22.64 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:23.04 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:23.86 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:26.96 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:46:32.33 USH - - - - Idling
09:46:32.34 SWS - - - - Idling
09:46:32.36 LSH - - - - Idling
09:46:35.87 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:47:25.39 --- - - - - *** 19 deg
09:47:29.87 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:47:29.87 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:47:29.89 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:47:30.50 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:47:31.31 USH - - - - Idling
09:47:31.71 SWS - - - - Idling
09:47:32.52 LSH - - - - Idling
09:47:37.91 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:47:41.12 --- - - - - Reset shutters.

```

10:21:15.82	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:21:17.51	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:21:21.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:21.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:21.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:25.62	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:21:32.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:32.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:33.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:33.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:21:34.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:34.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:36.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:36.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:36.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:36.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:38.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:38.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:39.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:42.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:43.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:43.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:43.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:21:43.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:43.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:21:44.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:45.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:46.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:47.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:50.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:50.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:50.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:25.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:25.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:25.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:30.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:49:35.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:35.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:35.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:37.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:37.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:38.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:41.94	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:49:41.95	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:49:45.32	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:49:45.33	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:49:47.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:47.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:47.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:48.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:48.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:50.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:51.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:51.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:51.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:52.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:52.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:54.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:44.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:44.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:44.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:45.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:46.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:47.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:51.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:51.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:51.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:51.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:51.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

Time	Mode	Parameter 1	Parameter 2	Parameter 3	Parameter 4	Event
10:55:52.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:53.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:56.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:56.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:24.80	---	-	-	-	-	
10:57:24.80	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:57:24.80	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR /	Comment	+++				
10:57:24.80	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B419
10:57:24.80	---	-	-	-	-	
10:57:29.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
10:57:32.43	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:57:36.65	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:57:40.02	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:57:44.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:57:45.64	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:57:46.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:57:46.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:57:48.81	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:57:51.47	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:57:51.48	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:57:52.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:54.86	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:57:57.22	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:57:57.23	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:57:58.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:58.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:57:59.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:02.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:07.29	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:58:10.06	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:58:10.07	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:58:15.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:42.44	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:58:47.09	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:58:51.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:51.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:51.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:52.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:52.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:53.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:55.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:55.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:55.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:56.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:56.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:56.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:07.73	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
10:59:08.84	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:26:01.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:29:14.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:34:00.15	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:34:01.29	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:34:02.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:02.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:02.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:03.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:34:03.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:34:03.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:34:03.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:04.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:04.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:06.60	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:34:11.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:11.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:11.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:12.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:12.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:13.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:37:48.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:48.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:48.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:49.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:49.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:49.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:53.79	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:37:54.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:37:55.44	SWS	170.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:37:58.75	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:38:02.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:02.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:02.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:03.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:04.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:04.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:04.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:09.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1
11:40:09.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
11:40:22.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
11:40:57.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 19 deg
11:43:01.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
11:43:40.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** leaving cloud (CT were 3500 ft)
11:43:46.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 2700 ft
11:43:59.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
11:46:29.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 2 at 500 ft
11:46:35.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud run
11:46:39.05	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:46:40.73	SWS	-3.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:46:42.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:42.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:42.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:43.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:44.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:44.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:47.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:47.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:47.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:47.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:48.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:48.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:31.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
11:51:31.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:51:36.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
11:52:29.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
11:54:58.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3 at 3300 ft in cloud run
11:57:48.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:59:48.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:00:03.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:00:12.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to above cloud
12:00:46.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** above cloud
12:00:49.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:49.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:49.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:49.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:50.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:50.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:50.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:51.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:53.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:53.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:55.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:55.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:55.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:55.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:56.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:56.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:00:56.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:58.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:01:18.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 5 min above cloud run
12:01:30.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run at 4600 ft
12:02:08.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:04:11.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:06:36.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:06:47.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
12:07:29.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** clouf top 3800 ft
12:07:54.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:08:13.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 3100 ft
12:11:40.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
12:11:58.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5
12:12:45.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:13:10.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:13:33.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:33.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:33.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:34.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:35.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:35.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:44.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:16:29.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:29.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:29.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:30.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:30.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:30.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:33.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:33.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:33.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:34.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:34.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:35.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:49.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:49.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:49.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:49.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:50.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:50.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:50.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:18.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:22:27.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to 3500 ft
12:22:43.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:25:05.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 2900 ft
12:25:42.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3500ft
12:25:49.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run
12:28:15.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:15.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:15.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:16.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:16.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:17.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:19.66	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:28:21.30	SWS	171.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:28:24.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:24.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:24.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:25.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:25.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:26.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:08.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:30:57.69	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:30:59.39	SWS	-4.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:31:03.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:03.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:03.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:04.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:04.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:05.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:16.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run

12:36:06.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** correctio end of run now
12:36:14.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
12:36:46.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4100 ft
12:37:05.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:05.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:05.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:06.93	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:37:08.67	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:37:09.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:09.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:09.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:17.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:17.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:17.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:17.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:18.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:18.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:18.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:20.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:48.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** reverse at 5100 ft
12:37:54.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile down to 50 ft
12:38:04.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 8
12:38:19.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:38:59.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4000 ft
12:41:24.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 2500 ft
12:41:54.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:43:18.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 50 ft will move sws telescope to zenith
12:43:35.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:44:32.41	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:44:34.13	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:44:43.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 100 ft
12:46:52.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:52:01.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:01.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:01.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:02.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:02.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:03.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:05.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:05.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:05.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:05.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:06.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:06.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:18.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
12:57:19.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:57:27.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
12:57:38.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** p9
13:00:20.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
13:00:55.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p
13:02:25.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** syart of run
13:02:35.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 8
13:03:02.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:02.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:02.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:03.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:03.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:04.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:06.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:06.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:06.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:07.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:08.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:08.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:17.60	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:03:19.31	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:03:36.60	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:03:43.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
13:11:43.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:11:43.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:43.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:43.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:44.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:44.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:44.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:47.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:50.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:50.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:50.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:50.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:51.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:51.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:11.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** rb
13:12:33.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** point at which we were over the top of the ron brown
13:15:53.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:53.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:53.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:54.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:54.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:54.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:45.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 19 deg
13:21:07.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
13:22:01.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:22:25.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to 1000 ft above cloud, p10
13:22:38.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3900 ft
13:23:06.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:06.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:06.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:07.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:07.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:07.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:13.50	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:23:13.52	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:23:16.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:16.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:16.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:17.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:17.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:18.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:20.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:20.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:20.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:21.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:21.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:21.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:50.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 4900 ft
13:25:30.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
13:30:52.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:31:37.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:37.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:37.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:38.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:38.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:38.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:31.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:35:28.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run at 4800 ft
13:36:34.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3900 ft
13:38:02.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run 3200 ft
13:38:14.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 11
13:41:55.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:45:28.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:28.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:28.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:29.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:29.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:29.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:39.01	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000

13:45:40.77	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:45:42.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:42.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:42.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:43.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:44.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:44.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:46.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:47:26.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** over ron brown now
13:53:18.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
13:54:28.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:56:56.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:57:32.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
13:57:59.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:58:21.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 2500 ft
13:58:42.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p
13:58:48.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 2200 ft
13:59:40.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:40.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:41.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:41.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:41.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:42.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:59:42.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:44.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:47.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:47.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:47.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:47.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:47.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:48.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:48.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:59:49.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:59:51.93	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:59:53.66	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:59:54.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:54.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:59.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:59.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:59.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:00.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:00.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:01.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:29.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:01:13.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run
14:01:19.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 300 ft below cloud
14:01:23.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:23.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:23.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:24.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:24.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:25.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:31.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:31.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:31.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:33.40	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:01:35.15	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:01:36.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:36.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:36.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:38.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:38.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:38.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:39.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:39.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:40.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:40.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:41.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:46.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 12

14:03:42.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:08:20.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:09:38.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:11:33.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** over flying ron brown now
14:11:37.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:12:11.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:11.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:11.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:12.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:12.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:13.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:19.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:19.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:19.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:21.30	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:12:23.07	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:12:24.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:24.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:24.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:26.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:26.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:26.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:27.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:27.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:28.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:30.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:30.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:30.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:31.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:31.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:31.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:34.39	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:14:36.11	SWS	-5.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:14:38.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:38.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:38.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:38.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:14:39.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:39.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:14:40.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:42.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:54.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:21:43.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run and start of profile descent
14:24:28.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:28.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:28.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:29.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:29.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:30.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:34.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
14:26:43.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 100 ft
14:27:58.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
14:29:02.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:35:46.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:35:55.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:55.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:55.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:56.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:56.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:57.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:58.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:58.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:58.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:59.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:59.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:00.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:01.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:28.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:38.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:36:38.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:38.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:39.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:39.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:40.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:46.73	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:36:48.47	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:36:49.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:49.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:49.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:50.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:50.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:50.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:51.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:51.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:53.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:53.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:57.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:57.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:57.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:57.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:58.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:59.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:14.69	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:37:16.45	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:37:17.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:17.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:17.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:18.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:18.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:19.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:38.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:40:13.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 35 11 passed ron brown
14:41:22.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:22.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:22.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:23.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:23.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:24.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:15.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:44:59.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run and start of profile climb
14:45:02.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:45:09.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:09.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:09.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:09.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:10.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:11.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:13.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:13.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:13.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:14.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:14.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:15.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:42.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** thats was end of run 13 and start of profile 13
14:46:35.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
14:47:04.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:47:50.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 2700 ft
14:48:31.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:48:35.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:36.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:37.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:38.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:38.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:48:40.10	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
14:48:40.11	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
14:48:41.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:42.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:48:42.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:43.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:56.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3900 ft
14:50:42.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:42.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:42.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:43.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:44.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:44.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:50.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:55:55.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing profile at 6000 ft
14:55:57.68	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:55:59.45	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:56:01.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:01.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:01.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:01.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:02.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:02.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:11.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 14
15:00:40.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 6000 ft
15:00:43.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
15:04:32.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:04:38.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:38.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:39.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:39.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:39.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:40.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:04:40.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:42.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:44.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:44.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:44.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:45.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:46.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:46.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:27.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:09:38.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:09:50.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
15:09:53.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** p 15
15:12:13.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** skimming cloud tops at 4000 ft
15:13:48.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 12 01 start of run
15:15:22.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:16:14.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:16:32.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** now at 3850 ft
15:17:27.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:19:36.59	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:19:38.41	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:19:41.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:41.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:41.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:41.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:19:41.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:42.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:19:43.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:19:48.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:19:58.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:21:51.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** over on brown now
15:21:56.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:22:05.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
15:22:15.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 16 (end of run 15)
15:22:54.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
15:23:27.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base
15:23:38.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:23:46.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** CB 2500 ft
15:25:36.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:28:00.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft and start of profile climb
15:30:44.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg

15:31:35.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:31:53.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3900 ft
15:32:26.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile
15:32:31.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 4500 ft
15:32:37.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:37.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:37.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:38.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:38.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:38.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:39.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:32:40.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:40.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:41.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:41.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:41.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:42.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:32:44.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:48.71	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
15:32:48.72	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
15:32:50.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:50.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:51.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:51.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:52.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:52.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:54.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:54.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:54.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:55.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:55.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:56.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:56.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:33:05.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:10.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:36:03.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:39:51.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
15:40:44.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending for in cloud run
15:40:49.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** down to 3400 ft
15:41:03.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top
15:41:12.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction now
15:41:17.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** CT 3800 ft
15:41:41.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** run in cloud at 3400 ft
15:41:49.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
15:42:42.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** patchy cloud
15:42:49.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:43:03.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** now running at 3500 ft
15:44:07.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** going down to 3450 ft
15:47:25.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:51:42.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run, and profile descent to 1000 ft
15:52:10.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** that was end of run 16 start of profile 19
15:52:52.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:54:30.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:54:32.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:54:38.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:38.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:38.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:38.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:39.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:39.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:39.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:41.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:47.43	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
15:54:49.37	SWS	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
15:54:51.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:51.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:55.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:55.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:55.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:54:56.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:56.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:56.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:08.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile and start of run
15:55:17.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** patchy cloud above
15:57:11.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:57:21.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:21.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:21.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:22.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:23.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:23.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:09.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
16:05:08.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** en dof run
16:05:29.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb for above cloud run
16:07:28.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
16:07:52.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3300ft
16:08:04.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
16:08:27.50	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:08:30.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:30.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:30.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:30.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:31.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:32.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:32.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:34.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:35.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:35.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:35.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:36.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:36.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:37.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:42.34	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
16:08:42.35	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
16:08:42.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:08:46.49	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:08:48.26	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:08:49.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:49.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:49.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:49.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:50.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:50.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:11.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 4500 ft above boundary layer
16:09:14.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:14.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:14.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:16.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:16.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:16.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:17.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:17.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:17.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:18.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:19.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:19.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:34.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** patchy cloud below
16:09:46.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 18
16:10:13.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
16:10:31.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
16:12:58.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 4500 ft
16:13:06.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:06.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:06.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:07.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:08.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:08.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:10.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:13:10.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:10.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:11.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:12.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:12.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:12.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:13:15.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:29.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
16:15:52.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
16:19:12.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
16:19:19.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending to 50 ft
16:19:25.53	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:19:27.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:19:27.33	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:19:29.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:29.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:29.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:30.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:30.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:31.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:34.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:35.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:38.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:38.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:38.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:39.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:39.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:40.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:19:40.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:43.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:43.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:19:47.69	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 10ms.
16:19:47.70	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 10ms.
16:19:51.00	SWS	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:19:51.02	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:19:54.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:54.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:01.10	SWS	-	500	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 500ms.
16:20:04.84	SWS	-	4000	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 4000ms.
16:20:08.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:20:12.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:20:15.84	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:20:17.64	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:20:21.13	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:20:21.14	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:20:25.57	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 4000ms to 100ms.
16:20:29.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:30.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:32.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:32.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:33.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:33.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:34.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:34.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:35.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:35.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:36.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:36.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:36.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:04.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
16:22:04.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
16:22:28.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
16:22:42.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
16:24:40.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
16:25:24.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft, reversing sawtooth
16:25:28.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:25:28.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:25:28.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

16:25:29.77	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:25:31.54	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:25:33.62	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
16:25:33.63	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
16:25:35.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:35.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:35.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:35.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:25:40.37	SWS	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:25:40.38	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:25:45.78	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:25:47.56	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:25:49.75	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:25:49.76	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:25:53.29	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 40ms.
16:25:53.30	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 40ms.
16:25:56.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:56.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:56.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:57.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:57.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:57.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:34.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:34.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:34.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:35.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:35.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:36.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:29:19.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3350 ft
16:29:27.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
16:30:07.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
16:30:53.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** reverse climb at 5000 ft
16:31:04.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending to 500 ft
16:32:06.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
16:33:16.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top
16:33:34.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top was 3400 ft
16:33:48.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base
16:34:17.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:17.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:17.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:18.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:19.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:19.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:19.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:19.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:20.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:21.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:21.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:21.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:23.67	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 10ms.
16:34:23.69	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 10ms.
16:34:25.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:26.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:27.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:27.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:29.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:34:30.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:34:30.93	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:34:33.90	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
16:34:35.75	SWS	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:34:37.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:38.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:40.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:40.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:52.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:53.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:24.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing sawtooth at 500 ft
16:37:26.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:37:31.41	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000

16:37:33.20	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:37:34.07	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:37:36.87	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:37:36.88	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:37:38.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:38.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:40.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:40.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:40.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:41.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:41.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:41.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:43.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:43.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:43.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:44.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:44.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:45.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:48.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:37:49.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
16:37:55.99	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
16:37:56.00	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
16:37:57.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:58.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:59.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:00.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:10.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
16:38:13.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:13.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:13.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:38:14.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:38:18.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:18.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:18.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:26.25	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 25ms.
16:38:26.27	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 25ms.
16:38:29.38	SWS	-	-	45	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 45ms.
16:38:29.39	SWS	-	-	-	45	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 45ms.
16:38:32.68	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 45ms to 20ms.
16:38:32.71	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 45ms to 20ms.
16:38:46.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws doing very strange things
16:38:52.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** signal enermous
16:39:05.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** VIS has now dropped out completely
16:39:17.74	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:39:21.01	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:39:24.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:25.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:26.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:39:29.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:33.80	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 20ms.
16:39:36.20	SWS	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 600ms.
16:39:40.18	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 10ms.
16:39:43.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:43.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:44.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:45.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:49.16	SWS	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
16:39:51.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:52.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:52.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:53.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:57.50	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 20ms.
16:39:59.23	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 20ms.
16:40:02.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:03.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:04.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:05.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:31.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:31.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

16:40:31.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:33.52	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:40:35.30	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:40:36.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:36.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:36.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:37.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:40:40.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:40.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:40.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:42.58	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:40:44.34	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:40:45.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:45.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:45.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:55.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
16:44:00.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
16:44:06.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:44:06.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:44:06.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:44:07.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:44:09.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:44:18.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
16:44:19.50	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:55:24.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:28.40	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:55:29.57	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:55:39.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:55:39.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:55:40.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:55:41.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:41.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:42.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

Flight:

B419

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B419

Date: 12/11/08

Issues

1. BBRs- Upper Pyrgeometer signal / zero very noisy.
2. RFC/DFC bay – suspect water running down inside of RFC window
3. TWC – Detector signal occasionally topping out at 4095 around 1445Z onwards. Status bit 4094. Window needing cleaned?

Instruments

Dropsondes	Nil
CVI -	ok
Filters	ok
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
WetNeph	ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem	ok
Cloud physics -	ok PCASP channel 1 noisy otherwise scale error (leak) Ok
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	ok
SWS -	minor problems
CCN	ok, single channel only.
CPC	ok
PAN	ok
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

SatcomC	ok
MPDS	Run for flight, ok
ISDN Emails	Nil
Satcom-H Calls	Nil

B419 lwc run8

B419 lwc run15 cloud top

B419 lwc run10-11

B419 TWC run 15 bad cal

B419 theta-e profiles P14-16

b419 TEPHI P7-8

b419 TEPHI P21-22

b419 TEPHI P12-13a

b419 TEPHI P23-24

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B419:

Log	Reason
Pre-flighter log	No log available
De-brief	No debrief has been completed by the Mission Scientist
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CCN log	CCN operator does not create a log sheet
MARSS	No log as instrument went U/S
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS	2D-S / CAPS operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
PAN log	PAN operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_112925_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_122925_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_132925_1hz.av
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_142925_1hz.av
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_152925_1hz.av
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_162925_1hz.av

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_112917_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_122917_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_132917_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_142917_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_152917_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_162917_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_112914_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_122914_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_132914_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_142914_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_152914_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_162914_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_112921_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_122921_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_132921_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_142921_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_152921_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081112_r0_b419_162921_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.